

WIMEA-ICT RC3

EVALUATION REPORT ON BERGEN PROTOTYPE

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Abstract

Research Component 3 (RC3) in the WIMEA-ICT project has its primary task as the design of an affordable automatic weather station (AWS), arranging for manufacture and the mass deployment of 70 such units in several areas around East Africa.

A draft version of such an AWS, called the Bergen Prototype, has so far been put together by some of the RC3 advisors and has been operational for some months now. The PhD students on this team, who are the authors of this document, have been tasked with the review of this prototype to determine what could be changed to make the design more optimal in several areas such as software, hardware, power consumption and communication.

This document presents the issues found in our analysis and various recommendations that will be discussed and agreed upon to make way for the second generation prototype, which we shall call the East African prototype.

Section 1 begins with an introduction on how each evaluation was done. Section 2 discusses the evaluation of the topology in use and recommendations. Section 3 discusses the gateway and gives recommendations and Section 4 discusses a few issues that could merit concern in the general design and some matters arising and finally, section 5 contains references to several documents that we consulted in this matter.

1. Introduction

In each section, we will look at the technology in use in the Bergen prototype, compare with alternatives using manufacturer based data, our user experiences and the experiences of our advisors.

Some sections will recommend benchmarking experiments while others may give straight up conclusions and recommendations, either because the justifications are straightforward or simply because the alternatives will not provide much improvement in cost or performance or other parameters in the remaining time.

2. Topology

2.1 Introduction

By Topology, we refer to the use of a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), or wireless transmission of data in general as opposed to a scenario in which the sensors are connected directly to the gateway by conductors.

Wired connections are in use in several AWS across East Africa according to the surveys that were undertaken from November 2014. Nowadays, WSNs have emerged as a robust and popular technology. Each of these types has advantages and disadvantages. We present a comparison in both types based on the following properties, which we believe are characteristics of a good connection or network.

1. **Scalability:** Ideally, the system should allow unrestricted sensor node placement. With the current topology, it is much easier to install a sensor rather than in a wired network, which would need physical intrusion from cabling and attaching the sensor node onto the AWS frame. This is also very useful if a mote fails during operation. Another similar mote can just simply be placed near the station without the need to physically access it.
2. **Reliability:** This has to do with the fraction of data that eventually reaches the gateway with integrity, either because the packets are lost along the way or the transmitting device is faulty. Reliability is typically achieved by retransmission and/or redundancy by adding extra nodes or sensors [1]. The risk of losing data in a wired network is lower, since we have a direct connection. This connection however is a point of failure, as it is a solid channel that could break. In wireless transmission however, it is rare that the medium itself (air) is faulty. In both wired and wireless cases, retransmission of data is possible. To achieve redundancy however, the logistical challenges to be met in a wired network are far greater because of the issues presented in item (1).
3. **Cost:** The cost of setting up the link should be as low as possible. The cost of the cabling and labor is a disadvantage for wired connections. To the contrary, wireless devices are

now very cheap and are scalable as explained in (1). As such, it may be much cheaper to set up wireless connections.

4. **Range:** A good network should be able to cover a long range. Long range connections may be a challenge for wired connection because of voltage drops and the need for more cable length. Wireless sensor nodes may be able to send data over several tens or hundreds of metres with good reception at the gateway, depending on the protocol in use.
5. **Power consumption:** The rule of thumb is that the consumption should be as low as possible. Active wired sensors will consume from the same power source as the gateway, or from the gateway itself. Wireless sensor nodes need their own power supply thus making them points of failure. In an absolute sense, the need for a separate power supply for the wireless sensor node is a disadvantage unless special techniques are used to preserve the power for as long as possible.
6. **Security:** Data sniffing should not be possible. In the particular case of an AWS with sensors wired to the gateway, the possibility of eavesdropping on the data is very unlikely. Wireless channels however should be protected from sniffing by various encryption methods.
7. **Support for various topologies:** When using wired sensors, we are limited to one topology which is a star topology. If the link between the gateway and the sensor breaks, no access to the sensor is possible. In wireless sensor networks, we are not be limited to one design as we can have both single hop or multi-hop transmission. Even when a link to the gateway is broken, data from a sensor node can reach the gateway through intermediate nodes.
8. **Immunity to the environment:** There are several issues to consider here.
 - i. First is the natural environment. During thunderstorms, wires from sensor nodes to the gateway act as radio antennas in a wider radio spectrum such that the electromagnetic radiation from lighting higher than the microwave frequencies might lead to electrical disturbance that would easily destroy nodes and the gateway [2]. In such a case, wireless links are superior to wired links. The same applies in cases such as fire and landslides.
 - ii. Second is the human environment. Wireless connections are “cut-resistant” connections. Before a human being can cut a connection, they have to know that it is there. Thus, as opposed to wired links, the invisibility of wireless connections enables the creation of networks and links that are extremely hard to disrupt deliberately or by accident.

2.2 Matters arising

The Bergen prototype uses wireless sensor nodes connected to a gateway in a single hop architecture. Any advantages and disadvantages put forward for wireless links in the previous section will apply. A major issue to consider in this decision is that specifications on the sensors or on the number of parameters to measure could change after installation. Making the topology scalable would be a huge advantage in this regard.

It is our opinion that the combined benefits of using wireless links between the sensors and gateway outweigh the disadvantages.

However, some pertinent issues that arise from our user experiences so far are now put forward.

1. Reliability

- i. The current design is based on a single-hop topology, in which each node broadcasts a radio packet directly to the gateway via the sink-node. As such, if the sink-node fails then the entire system is disrupted. The benefits of using a redundant sink node to increase the reliability should be weighed against the cost and any other parameters.
 - ii. Following from the above, a single-hop technology also means that if the link between a node and the gateway is broken, say from displacement of the node or low power supply to the node, communication is disrupted. A multi-hop architecture could ensure that sensor data is relayed through nearby nodes to the active sink node.
 - iii. It is not mentioned anywhere whether retransmission of data is currently being employed. If it is not, it is probably justified because the distances of the nodes from the gateway are very small and the probability of data being received is very high. Moreover, it may not be necessary depending on the sampling time interval of the sensors. If there is sufficient evidence that these distances could increase to levels at which packet loss becomes common, then the use of this technique should be investigated.
2. **Security:** The motes broadcast IEEE 802.15.4 packets formatted with a tag-style encoding, in plain ASCII, with device addresses and data [4]. This setup can be easily sniffed upon by any similar device developed for this purpose. Using a standard encryption algorithm for this data may protect the data but increase the overhead and produce large packets that may have to be sent in parts. Un-tagging the data can improve security, since the information becomes meaningless to the sniffer, but would require a legend to be kept at the gateway or remote server to explain which values mean what—and the legend would have to change each time the report changes. A suitable means of protecting the sensor data needs to be investigated, starting with the crypto engine of the ATMEGA128RFA1 in use on the motes.

3. Power consumption

The main issue here is that the sink node is always on and that causes a major power concern. Power savings can be achieved by the use of well-timed sleep/wake up modes such that the sink node is asleep when all motes are asleep and awake when any of the motes is awake. This requires some form of clock synchronization across the entire system.

2.3 Recommendation for Topology

It is our recommendation that the use of wireless links between the sensors and gateway be retained in the East African prototype. Power savings should be achieved by using sleep/wake up cycles on the sink node.

The use of a redundant sink node and a multi-hop architecture, with a secure channel, can be considered. Since security and hopping are software considerations and do not need any extra hardware, there is ample time to investigate these during the testing and manufacturing phases of the AWS.

It is also our recommendation that the current motes in use, the Universal IEEE 802.15.4 mote, be retained. There are several reasons for this:

- i. There is evidence of a great deal of design effort and testing that has already been put into the device. There have been two board revisions and several firmware revisions. We believe that there is not much improvement an alternative design would bring to the table compared to the man-hours it would need to make such a design which could be spent on other AWS design issues.
- ii. Free ADC channels make the device scalable and several sensors can be mounted on a single mote, thus reducing the total number of required motes
- iii. The mote has already met several safety and RF approvals on the European continent.
- iv. The mote has already been extensively tested in several similar deployments in-field and there is evidence of it running continually in an AWS prototype for several months without major issues. We can infer some degree of reliability from this.
- v. It is small, portable and has very good power consumption during active and sleep periods. In one application, it has been shown to go for six weeks on a single supercapacitor [5].
- vi. It is based on a common microcontroller (ATMEGA128) with free development tools and a large community of users. Writing custom firmware for the device is possible at anytime.

3 Gateway

To arrive on an appropriate choice of gateway to use in the EA prototype, we discussed from scratch the following issues:

- i. the function of the gateway
- ii. the desirable properties the gateway should have

3.1 Functions

The following are the functions of the gateway.

- i. Receive and store data from local sensors
- ii. Send data from local sensors to (remote) server
- iii. Receive data from server. These data can be commands, acknowledgement information, firmware updates, etc.

3.2 Desirable properties

The following properties are desirable to have in the gateway considering that the bulk of the stations will be located in remote areas, away from immediate human intervention.

1. **Low power consumption.**

This is an extremely important property. Energy is a constrained resource.

- The consumption should be as low as possible compared to the ability of the power source.
 - The power consumption during active mode should be low but more important is its consumption during inactive mode (see item 2).
2. The gateway should have an **on-demand low-power inactive mode** (standby/hibernate/shutdown) that can be triggered by software or hardware. This directly affects power consumption and is desirable because measurements and transmissions of data will be happening continually and not continuously.
 3. The gateway **boot and wake-up time** should be as low as possible. This is because bulk of the power consumed in active mode should be for “real work”, such as data reception and transmission, and not initialization overheads.
 4. In case the uplink to the server is down, the gateway should have a **local data storage** facility.
 5. In general, the gateway’s form factor should be conducive to the whole design process, starting from placement of peripherals to selection of the housing.
 6. **Perform diagnostic service and give reports** of itself and sensors connected to it. This property is desirable as it allows for remote monitoring and troubleshooting
 7. The gateway should be a well tested product from a credible manufacturer.
 8. The gateway should support **networking and a file system** at the bare minimum. This is because of its storage and communication functions.
 9. The gateway should be **affordable** compared to the WIMEA-ICT budget.

3.3 Matters arising

The desirable properties will now be weighed against the current gateway in the Bergen prototype, the Raspberry Pi, and with other possible contenders, and recommendations given.

1. **Power consumption:** While the consumption of the Pi is quite low compared to other devices used in personal computing (which was main design philosophy behind it [6]), there are several devices that could be programmed to achieve the functions mentioned in 3.1 while running at a fraction of its power. More importantly, since the gateway will be performing its functions in a small amount of time and be inactive for the larger part, the power consumption in this period also matters. The Pi, per se, does not have a sleep mode and when idle consumes about 1100mW [7]. Moreover, the sink node is always on thus adding onto the total consumption. A gateway that operates in the microwatt ranges during idle time, such as those based on the STM32 family [8], can be achieved. In fact, several 32 bit ARM Cortex devices are good contenders as they come with various sleep modes and consume ultra-low currents during active and sleep modes. Examples are the FM4 family from Cypress Semiconductor [9] and the EFM32 family from silicon labs [10].
2. **Low power inactive mode.** As already mentioned, such a mode, strictly speaking, does not exist in the Raspberry Pi. Modifications would have to be made, such as adding a daughter board to turn off the gateway when not in use. This obviously adds onto the number of peripherals, and thus affects initial design time, portability, aesthetics, points of failure and cost. Moreover, the consumption of the daughter board itself must be investigated. A major issue that also arises from this how soon the gateway can be used once it is turned on again.
3. **Wake up time:** The Pi, since it does not support the halt or suspend functions, wake up essentially means boot if it is modified as suggested in (ii). The boot time on a minimal linux system is currently being investigated currently by the PhD students but some users have reported boot times (both kernel and user space) of about 8 seconds running minimal Linux systems [11]. Such times are of course much larger than those achievable using "bare metal" development. The same STM32 family talked about earlier has wake up times in the order of microseconds.[8]
4. **Local data storage:** The Pi's memory is sufficient for this application. Almost all contemporary microcontrollers support some kind of file system or at least an SPI interface to which an SD card can be attached. As an example, the sensors.dat file (which holds data received from the sensors) is currently at just under 90MB after several months of data collection in the Bergen prototype. A 4GB removable card could be sufficient to hold several years of data. As the file size increases, its access time also increases so a good idea could be to store the data in separate files up to a given maximum. Alternatively, once we can confirm that the data was successfully uploaded to the server, it could be deleted after a specified time and data redundancy could be delegated to RC2.

5. **Form factor:** This is a challenge given that there are several interfaces on the Pi that shall not be useful in this application. The HDMI port, 2 or 3 USB ports, the audio jack and the Ethernet port are all unnecessary—the last being due to the fact that in a remote area, the uplink will most probably be a cellular or other wireless service. If we are to design for portability and proper mechanical support, the gateway microcontroller, its power supply and other peripherals should be on the same PCB. This also improves aesthetics and eliminates the chances of loose connections and conductor breakage at interface points. Designing the PCB for chip level connections will also enable flexibility of component placement around the processor.
6. **Diagnostic Services:** It is possible to log onto the Pi in the Bergen prototype and perform some diagnostic and troubleshooting operations. If the gateway will be going to sleep for some time and waking up again, the connection procedure becomes more complex as it will have to be timed accurately. Hence, a possible solution would be to schedule regular diagnostic reports from the gateway, the contents of which can be agreed upon later (online notes, voltages, RSSI values, dead sensors etc). Also, there will be several AWS installed. It will be much faster looking for faults by querying and data mining the report information sent to the server rather than attempting to log onto individual AWSs.
7. **Credible Manufacturer:** The Pi's comes from a credible manufacturer features open source hardware and software and a vibrant community. This is also the same case with many other computing platforms.
8. **Networking and a file system.** The Pi is OS based and so supports these as a basic function. The Bergen prototype currently uses an Ethernet connection to the internet and this would necessitate a TCP/IP stack. However, with the use of a GPRS/3G module, low level networking operations are left to the module's processor and connection from the gateway to the module are at a system level. File system support for common removable devices (FAT16/FAT32) is also a basic feature on several contemporary microcontrollers.
9. **Affordability:** The Raspberry Pi is rather cheap since in this application no general purpose computing peripherals are needed. Several microprocessors, already on their development boards, cost just as much as the Pi, or vary only slightly. The cost of the gateway itself, however, is not representative of the total cost of developing the gateway system which will include PCB design and electronic peripherals that may even be more expensive than the gateway device itself.

3.4 Recommendation

It is our belief that the primary functions of the gateway can be performed at a fraction of the power currently being consumed by the Raspberry Pi while implementing several of the desirable properties within the remaining time frame of the Bergen visit.

We suggest that power consumption be considered the primary parameter in selecting the gateway. Power consumption is also important because there may be a possibility of panel-

less installations in order not to attract vandals, a major problem seen with the AWSs installed in Uganda have faced [12]. As such, an experiment should be conducted using devices whose datasheets suggest a consumption of much less power, such as those suggested in [8],[9],[10] and yet meet the majority of the desirable properties, against which the Pi has also been evaluated. The manufacturer provided data for such devices, on paper, is enough to justify such an experiment. Such a device will be programmed to achieve the bare minimum AWS functionality (receive data, store and transmit), and its power consumption benchmarked against the Raspberry Pi.

If the savings are significant then it is our recommendation that the alternative be taken.

4 Other issues

We now move our discussion to other design issues that we felt would be important for evaluation.

4.1 RS Mote Power Supply

The nodes are currently being powered by solar panels charging ultracapacitor batteries. The current solar panels in use are quite sizeable, and would find a number of household uses in rural East Africa which may cause the vandalism spoken about in [12]. A design to consider is to use very small 2.5-3.5V, 40-100mA solar panels (~ 60mm x 60mm or similar) with a basic charge controller to the capacitor. Such small panels would deter vandals—and solar energy resource in East Africa is available for long durations throughout the day on many days so small charging currents are not necessarily a disadvantage.

4.2 Node Enclosure

The IP rating for the enclosure casings currently in use to protect the motes and internal circuits from dust and water is not available but from our recent experiences, seems satisfactory. The main worry is how this rating is affected by any drilling done to permit the passage of conductors. We suggest the use of standard drill bits and standard cable glands to create IP68 compliant enclosure boxes for the electronics.

4.3 Conduction and Radiation shielding

The manufacturers of the SHT2X sensor family have some general guidelines for best practices while using their sensors [13]. It would seem that some of these practices are intended for high precision measurements and their disregard may probably not cause issues that later calibration will not fix. However, it seems to be a general guideline to thermally decouple the sensor from heat sources on the PCB (usually, other electronics) by mounting the sensor on its own board and then connecting this board to the main board or using a flex in the PCB—see figure 8 in [13]. We suggest this as an issue to discuss, especially with RC1.

We are aware that the RC3 advisors have developed a radiation shield for this sensor and we await a demonstration of this.

4.4 Frame

The Prototype currently has no Frame onto which the gateway and some sensor nodes will be mounted. In the initial deployment, some sensors were mounted on an already existing AWS from another manufacturer. Generally, the frame should be weather resistant and physically strong. Our research has revealed several materials that could be used, including but not limited to:

- i. Stainless steel
- ii. Lightweight Carbon fibre
- iii. Aluminium
- iv. A mixture of any of these

It may be necessary for this team to make a specific survey of few weather stations installed in Bergen directed to study the materials used and other general frame design principles.

5 References:

1. Mahmood M.A et al, Reliability In Wireless Sensor Networks: A Survey and Challenges ahead, *The International Journal of Computer and Telecommunications Networking*, vol. 79 (2015) pp. 166–187, Online. [6 January 2015].
2. Pehrson, B., Olsson,R., *WIMEA-ICT Research Component 3, Progress Report 2014*, pp.5
3. Toscano, E., Lo Bello, L., Cross-Channel Interference in IEEE 802.15.4 Networks, IEEE Workshop on Factory Communication Systems, May 2008, pp. 139-148
4. Osslon, R., A practical Guide to Wireless IEEE 802.15.4 Monitoring. http://hejulf.se/products/WSN/sensors/wsn_practical_guide.html (Accessed: 28 Aug 2015)
5. Olsson, R., Perhson, B., Powering devices using ultra-capacitor batteries, AFRICON 2015
6. <https://www.raspberrypi.org/help/what-is-a-raspberry-pi/> (Accessed 27 Aug 2015)
7. Nungu, A., et al, Towards single watt nJoule/bit Routing, UbuntunetConnect 2014, Lusaka (+ Addedum: in Email from bpehrson@kth.se to authors, Jul 18 2015)
8. ST Microelectronics AN4365 Application Note, Page 8. http://www.st.com/st-web-ui/static/active/en/resource/technical/document/application_note/DM00096220.pdf (Accessed 27 Aug 2015)
9. <http://www.spansion.com/Products/microcontrollers/32-bit-ARM-Core/Pages/Default.aspx> (Accessed September 1 2015)
10. <http://www.silabs.com/products/mcu/lowpower/Pages/32-bit-microcontroller-technology.aspx#low-power> (Accessed September 1 2015)
11. <http://www.samplerbox.org/article/fastbootrpi> (Accesed 27 Aug 2015)
12. Nsabagwa, M., Byamukama M., Report On The Status Of Weather Stations In Uganda, May 2015
13. Sensirion AG, SHTxx Design Guide, <http://www.sensirion.com/nc/en/products/humidity-temperature/download-center/?cid=881&did=115&sechash=f65f6b63> (Accessed 27 Aug 2014)